

REVIEW ON PHYTOCHEMICAL AND PHARMACOLOGICAL SCREENING OF ABRU PRECATORIUS FOR MIGRAINE THERAPY

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ABSTRACT

Abrus precatorius (commonly known as Gunja, Chanoti, or Indian Licorice) is a medicinal plant traditionally employed in the management of various ailments, including migraine and headache. In folk medicine, root and leaf preparations have been used for analgesic purposes, while contemporary research is investigating its bioactive constituents for potential antimigraine activity. Researchers have investigated Abrus precatorius leaf to assess their potential efficacy in the management of migraine.

INTRODUCTION

Traditionally the leaves and roots of Abrus precatorius have been used in folk medicine in Afro-Asian regions to relieve localized pain, inflammation, and headaches. Leaf extracts or fresh leaf juice have traditionally been used as topical

preparation for the relief of neuromuscular discomfort. Modern pharmacological investigations have focused on the plant's bioactive phytochemicals to determine their neurological activity, especially their efficacy against migraine. It is strongly recommended that Abrus precatorius not be used for self-medication of migraine without appropriate medical or qualified herbal supervision.

Fig. 1: abrus precatorius plant leaf.

PLANT PROFILE

Abrus precatorius L.

Synonym	Rosary pea, Crab's eye, Jequirity bean, Precatory bean, and Indian licorice
Botanical name	<i>Abrus precatorius</i> L.
Family	Fabaceae
Geographical source	Tropical and subtropical regions of Asia (specifically India and Southeast Asia) and Africa.
Vernacular names	English: Rosary pea Tamil: Kundu Mani Hindi: Ratti Kannada: Gulaganji

Fig. 2: *Abrus precatorius* L.

Phytochemical constituent

Flavonoids - Apigenin, Naringenin, Hispidulin, Cirsimaritin

Terpenoids- Triterpenoids, Triterpene glycosides

Protein- Abrin, Abrus agglutinin

Alkaloids- Abrine, Trigonelline, Choline, Precatorine, Hepaphotine, Abrol, Abra sine, Precasine.

PHYTOCHEMICAL SCREENING METHODS FOR ABRUS PRECATORIUS

1. Test for alkaloids

- Dragendorff's test Take the leaf extract > Add few drops dragendorff's > Orange or reddish-brown precipitate.
- Mayer's test Take the leaf extract > Add few drops Mayer's > cream or pale-yellow precipitate.

2. Test for flavonoids

- Alkaline reagent test Take the leaf extract > Add few drops of sodium hydroxide > yellow colour that disappears on adding dilute acid.

3. Test for proteins amino acids

- Biuret test Take the leaf extract > Add few drops of biuret > violet or purple colour.
- Ninhydrin test Take the leaf extract > Add few drops of ninhydrin > purple or blue.

4. Test for steroids terpenoid

- Salkowski test Take the leaf extract > add few drops of Salkowski > reddish brown ring.

PHARMACOLOGICAL ACTIVITIES

➤ Anti- migraine

The anti-migraine activity of this plant has been reported to involve inhibition of serotonin, a neurotransmitter implicated in migraine pathophysiology. In addition, the plant extract may modulate the other neurotransmitters, including dopamine γ -aminobutyric acid (GABA), both of which participate in the regulation of migraine and headache. Furthermore, it may exert smooth muscle relaxant and antispasmodic effects, which could contribute to migraine relief.

➤ Neuromuscular activity

Extract of abrus precatorius L. have been reported to induce neuromuscular blockade, suggesting potential therapeutic utility in conditions such as tetanus. In addition, the extract

may exhibit new protective properties, which could be beneficial in the prevention or attenuation of neurodegenerative disorders, including Alzheimer's and Parkinson's disease. The muscle relaxant activity of abrus extract may also be useful in the management of muscle spasms and cramps. However, at high doses, these extracts may cause dose -dependent muscle weakness and paralysis due to their neuromuscular blocking effects.

➤ **Anti inflammatory**

The anti-inflammatory potential of abrus precatorius has been attributed to the presence of bioactive compounds such as abruslactone and abrusodides. In addition, researchers have identified two triterpenoid saponins, namely saponin one, saponin two, which may also contribute to its anti-inflammatory activity.

➤ **Immunodulating**

Abrus precatorius has been reported to exhibit immunomodulatory activity, indicating its ability to alter or regulate immune system responses. Extract of abrus precatorius has been shown to enhance the activity of immune cells, including macrophages, lymphocytes, and natural killer (NK) cells.

This immunostimulatory effect may promote antibody production, thereby strengthening host defence against infection.

In addition, the plant appears T-cells and macrophages, leading to improved phagocytic activity, which engulf and destroy pathogens. The immunomodulatory properties of Abrus precatorius has been associated with bioactive constituents such as abrin, agglutinin, and glycyrrhizin.

➤ **Immunostimulanting**

Abrin -B, a lectin isolated from the seeds of Abrus precatorius, induces strong cell agglutination. The degree of agglutination increases with the level of cellular differentiation. At nontoxic doses, abrin may enhance host immune responses, as evidenced by an increase in total leukocyte count and the weights of thymus and spleen.

CONCLUSION

The phytochemical and pharmacological evidence reviewed Abrus precatorius possesses several bioactive constituents with potential relevance to migraine management. The presence of flavonoids, alkaloids, saponins, tannins, terpenoids, and other secondary metabolites may

contribute to antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, analgesic, and neuroprotective effects, which are important mechanisms in migraine pathophysiology. Preclinical findings indicate that extracts of *Abrus precatorius* may modulate pain pathways, reduce oxidative stress, and attenuate neuroinflammatory responses, thereby supporting its traditional use in headache related disorders. Therefore, *Abrus precatorius* represents a promising candidate for further investigation as a source of novel antimigraine agents.

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